

CYBER SECURITY IN TRAVEL, TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY

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Abstract. *Today, tourism is popular in many countries around the world. Tourism is usually organized by tourism routes through tourism organizations. There are many types and forms of tourism: domestic, international, amateur tourism, organized tourism, travel somewhere nearby, distant travel, tourism aimed at expanding knowledge, climbing, water tourism, automotive tourism, walking tourism, sports tourism, and so on.*

Uzbektourism is still operating in the tourism industry in Uzbekistan, formed on July 27, 1992. Today it is called the Ministry of Tourism and Cultural Heritage of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The company's main task is to develop tourism infrastructure, build modern tourist complexes with foreign investment, develop new tourist destinations, expand the range of services, and so on. (motas.uz)

Keywords: *Uzbektourism, Cybersecurity, Internet*

Introduction

Cybersecurity is the practice of protecting critical systems and sensitive data from digital attacks. Cybersecurity measures, also known as information technology security, were designed to combat threats against networked systems and applications, and threats came from inside or outside the organization. Cybersecurity is one of the most important concerns regarding expanding internet technologies, products, services, and networks (Sharma et al., 2023). As the travel and tourism sector becomes increasingly digitalized and supports emerging technologies (such as artificial intelligence, the internet of things, and the cloud) to launch and redefine services, products and consumer experiences, their cyber ecosystems are increasingly vulnerable to the security and security risks associated with these technologies (Paraskevas, 2022). This high vulnerability is mainly due to the presence of many fragmented and heterogeneous business sectors that use a lot of technology in manufacturing and operation and are subject to cyber-attacks.

Currently, recent research shows that cybercrime or cyberattacks have increased greatly over the past decade (Dr. Zahed Ghaderi, 2023), while tourism and hospitality organizations rank third in compromise events after retail businesses and financial institutions (Trustwave, 2019). The evidence suggests that the damage is huge and imposes financial costs. For example, the data breach incident suffered a loss of \$ 2,4 million at Rosen Hotels and Resorts in 2016, prompting legal claims from credit card companies and customers (Dr. Zahed Ghaderi, 2023).

Inadequate cyber security exposes tourism and hospitality organizations, as well as customers, to high risks, and the availability of many types of data and applications makes the tourism industry a necessary target for cyber criminals. For example, self-service kiosks, mobile online payment systems, electronic systems and more customer engagement technology have been developed and designed to demonstrate innovation and convenience; Yet these complex technologies also reinforce the vulnerability and capacity for enemies to disrupt the systems of travel and tourism organizations (Dr. Zahed Ghaderi, 2023). Cybersecurity is not just about technology; people and information, systems and processes, politics, culture, and the physical environment are also involved. Thus, tourism organizations need to create a safe cyberspace

culture for their employees, partners, suppliers and customers, but they must remain resilient in the event of an attack.

While cyber security is also significantly more important in terms of supply and demand, while much evidence suggests that the travel and tourism systems are highly vulnerable to cybersecurity risks, ironically it is limited to both academics and practitioners. Tourism literature shows important research gaps that are a great place for empirical and conceptual research that sheds light on different aspects of cybersecurity and tourism. It is especially important to develop more robust models and theories that can enlighten the future path, and enhance our understanding of the issue of tourism and cybersecurity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that considering the above discussion and research gaps, the purpose of this Special Issue is to start cutting-top research articles on the risks of cybersecurity in travel, tourism and hospitality and how these challenges can be overcome in an era of increasing cyber-attacks. For this Special Issue, the editors offer strict theoretical and empirical research articles that provide a better understanding of cybersecurity and travel and tourism. We are interested in high-quality presentations with framings of different people who master various methodological approaches and theoretical conditions, rich new single and cross-country data sets, and use exogenous shocks to investigate the impact of cybercriminals, attacks and risks on travel, tourism and hospitality.

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